

LEGEND

Cross Hatched Area-
Surveyed 1968-
1970.

Shaded Area-
Projected Survey
1970-1971.

Scale 1:4,500,000

0 50 100 150
Kilometres

To Isfahan
and Jibal

To Basra
and Iraq

THE
GREAT
DESERT

SEISTAN
Zarang

To Sind

ZAGROS

MOUNTAINS

MAKRAN

PERSIAN GULF

BANDAR
DEYLAM

Shiraz

Istakhr

Sirjan

Kirman

Bam

Bushehr

Jiruft

Siraf

Lavan Is.

Hormuz
Is.

Minab

Henderabi Is.

Henjam Is.

Bahrein Is.

Qeshm Is.

Kish Is.

Jask

OMAN

